

The Feminine Sensibilities in Kamala Markandaya's Select Novels

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Abstract

The research paper explains the female writers feel that women have been poor victims of male domination and exploitation. So, the reality of the miserable plight of women, anguish and unspoken feelings encouraged them to voice their problems through the medium of writing in fiction in English. Being the women, they can dive deep into their psyche and understood their grievances. Therefore, feminism in literature has brought a new awakening, awareness to the people exclusively for women as literature gives a sense of reality. In the post-independence era women novelists have marked their presence by highlighting feminist issues in their writings. Among the galaxy of writers Nayantara Sahgal, Anita Desai, Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Pravar Jhabvala, Shashi Deshpande, Kamala Das, Bharti Mukherjee registered themselves as the successful novelists of Indian English fiction. They have projected the suffocated psyche of their protagonists by the virtue of their feminine sensibility and psychological insight. They have exposed their problem and the cause of their psychological and emotional imbalance. Women of the contemporary era feel inhibited to raise their voice against the male dominated society. They have sketched that women in spite of being highly educated undergo traumatic experiences due to repression. The feminine sensibilities in the novels of Kamala Markandaya depicted as narrators, opponents for male. They can find out the path to dilute the uncontrollable angry against male. From their works, they can insult and irritate the male character like taking revenge through the story narration. Kamala Markandaya's novels, in comparison with those of her contemporary women writers, seem to be more fully reflective of the awakened feminine sensibility in modern India as she attempts to project the image of the changing traditional society. The variety and complexity of the achieved content of her novels represent a major trend in the history of the Indo - English novel. Kamala Markandaya is one of the most outstanding woman novelists on the canvas of Indo-Asian fiction. She is undoubtedly one of the major novelists on the commonwealth scene.

Keywords: woman as mother, wife, daughter, employee, unfulfilled expectations, love and marriage, family relationship, exploitation, patriotism, attainment of freedom.

Kamala Markandaya projects the image of national consciousness on many levels of aesthetic awareness, the complication of her family, and personal feelings and emotions. Likewise, many female characters are appearing and fighting for their rights through the literary works. The author herself transmute into the character with her feeling and emotions in her novels. Though she is a post-independence female novelist, her novels touched the east and west cultural conflicts, women empowerment and used many images like

house and she is close to the women in different and its condition during the contemporary life and expresses her feeling, notions and ideas with power.

Nectar In A Sieve has been translated into seventeen languages which brought her worldwide fame. Markandaya is such a novelist who exemplifies the different kinds of women in her novels. She depicts peasants, westernized women, English women, spiritual women, prostitution, selfish and selfless women. As the title shows all the feminine qualities and their anguish in her novels. The motherly touch in Rukmani, Kunti, Ira, Sarojini, Nalini, Mohini shows the maternal instinct found in all women as common. They represent the realistic picture of a mother in society. The good mother and evil mother are generally found. Markandaya has succeeded in drawing attention towards the prevailing modernity during the contemporary days. Her modern characters like Mira, Lalitha, Saroja are seen today. They resemble other women working in private company or being home makers. She also traces the disadvantages and evils of extreme modernity. India is a spiritual country and being an Indian, Markandaya presents spiritual characters like Sarojini and Swami. The effect and loss of the spiritual values are showing very clearly through the eyes of the novelists characters.

In Her ten novels, Markandaya presents the vivid description of India after independence. The female characters are from the rural and urban places. For instance, her character Mira in "Some Inner Fury" 1955, "Nowhere Man", Caroline in "Possession" 1963, In "Nectar In A Sieve", Rukmani struggles in a changing village and is shown as exploited. In "A Silence Of Desire", Sarojini Dandekar battles between tradition and modernity in contemporary India, Nalini in "A Handful Of Rice". These characters are recognized in her novels. They are being the society women reflection as the common human beings. In her novels, she portrays the rural and urban scene, spiritual quest, modernism, attitude toward feminine superiority, East - West encounter, conflict between tradition and prevailing modernism and somewhat historical attitudes and also deals with the theme of "Spiritualism, mysticism, pious and holy notions, the rural and urban areas of South India and its conflicts in regard to both Indian and British, since many features are overviewed in her novels, the superiority of female has been discussed in her novels in regard to the male tendency to be superior.

However Kamala markandaya shrewdly presents the female characters in her novels in the village and city. she can be favourably compared with foreign novelists of distinction. Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao, Bhabani Bhattacharya, Manohar malgonkar, Kamala Markandaya and Ruth Prawar Jhabvala are among many others. R. P. Jhabvala and Kamala Markandaya have excelled others in presenting young Indian women in love with foreigners.

Woman is the most adorable, meaningful and scarifying characters in every man's life like goddesses. The extraordinary grandeur that she embodies gets fully evolved and expressed in motherhood, provided she is able to rightly conceive, understand and make use of her motherhood, not just to 'mother' her children but for the enfoldment of the 'Spiritual Truth' within her. It is then that she transforms herself into a lighthouse of wisdom, a dynamo of 'Shakti' and a harbour of solace and peace. From then onwards her contributions to the welfare of her family get reflected in society in a subtle but powerful way. She then turns into an evolutionary force of unlimited possibilities, directly or indirectly guiding the destiny of mankind. It is said that behind every successful man stands a woman - as wife or mother.

Marriage is a bondage between two souls but now it is a compromise. Marriage between Rukmani and Nathan is an ideal while Mohini's relation with Bawaji Rao 3rd is illegal. Rukmani is honoured, respected and an ideal for others women. Getting married is an end in itself for many women and, in such circumstances, gainful employment becomes of secondary or no importance. A modern woman, however, would not mind combining work with marriage, where as a less modern woman would remain satisfied with being just a housewife.

Woman in India now enjoy equal status with man and there is a large percentage who still feel that women do not enjoy equality of status. Earlier, it was that thought man is 'by nature' superior to women and it is because of his superior physical strength that he holds a dominant status compared to that of woman Indian woman still believe in the natural superiority of man to a large extent. If many women feel that man is superior, it is because of their dependence and subordination to man but modernization brings in increasing in dependence and equality in the man - woman relationship. The more modern a woman is the greater is her belief in treating a husband as an equal partner than as an inferior or dominant partner. It may be pointed out that none of the women replied that the husband should be treated as an inferior partner. Indian culture puts heavy premium on the birth of a male child because it is said that a man cannot attain salvation unless his last rites are performed by a son. A writer points out that a woman's position as a 'mother of sons' gives her authority in the household. It also assumed here that with the onset of modernization this particular attitude would also undergo a change, and people would not distinguish between the birth of a male child and a female child. Emphasis on the birth of male child also points out the fact of the 'inferior' or subordinate position of woman to man.

The women seem to be walking on a sharp - edged knife. If they are a little below the expectation of their spouse, they are dubbed as backward and useless. she gains fulfillment and satisfaction from her life and at the same time not draw unwarranted comments and criticism and also maintain her status of independence, cooperation, amiability etc. According to the modern view there are two things that stand out as solid expressions of the advantages to a society when women get good education. woman has been presented either as the embodiment of endurance, understanding and sacrifice, or, being immune to a large extent to the cultural impact of the West, as custodian of Indian culture. It is her virtue that counts, not her beauty. Therefore, the highest aim of an Indian woman has been to sacrifice for her lawful husband her flesh and personal ambitions. Such as her heroine Mira in "Some Inner Fury" 1955 and Caroline in "Possession" 1963, are women of flesh and blood. Yet each is an embodiment of the totality her country is known for. Mira's dramatic rejection of her English lover when he sided with the English men is indicative of her preference for her nation to her personal love. It is reflected her personal life.

Indeed, women are superior to man because she has power as Rukmani in "Nectar In A Sieve", Mira in "Some Inner Fury" and Sarojini in "A Silence Of Desire". The 'mission' or the search for freedom, is the priority of the masculine, whereas the search for love is the priority of the feminine.

Three of Markandaya's novels "Nectar In A Sieve 1954, Some Inner Fury 1955 and Possession 1963, are presented in reminiscential mood. All the three narrators are women and the plots are circular".(K. SS. N. Rao)

Every time the story begins when the narrator gets into the mood of recollection and ends when the experiences of a whole conscious life leads her to a moment of decision to shake off her ambivalent attitude.

In "Nectar In A Sieve 1954, Rukmani narrates her life story beginning with her marriage in such a way as to depict concurrently the agony of the Indian peasants. After returning to the village Rukmani cast a longing glance on the expanse of time that had elapsed between her marriage and the death of her husband. But Nectar In A Sieve is more than Rukmani's autobiography : The critics analysis whether a woman is superior or inferior in its own way. Generally, it regards woman superior in heart and inferior in mind but in the present day, this preamble is changed. Woman is successful in all walks of life. Home is the safe place for woman but now she is a working woman and going outside.

Rukmani is the feminine Superior in her novels, markandaya evinces the woman as mother, wife, daughter and prostitute in her "Nectar In A Sieve". the protagonists have taken their own

place and projected as different types of woman as peasant woman, English woman, westernized woman and spiritual woman have their own superiority. Rukmani is a peasant woman and able to endure all sufferings. She is an idol of an Indian woman. Living in a village, she is literate and bears six children. She is superior both in heart and mind. She is different from other peasant ladies. Despite the difficulties, she could not involve in evils and keep her path clean while Kunti and Ira involve in prostitution. She becomes a good wife and a good mother. The marriage between Rukmani and Nathan was “a poor match.” (Markandaya Kamala p2) as it had been thought by Rukmani’s relatives and her village people. Even her mother was not happy with this marriage because it is below her social standard. In a village community, in setting marriages the social prestige and economic standard of the bridegroom family must be higher than that of the bride’s. Rukmani herself, at another place in the novel, describes the married life of Kunti who has also been “married beneath her”. (Markandaya Kamala p8) On the whole, Rukmani’s married life is happy despite the fact that her husband has illicit relations with Kunti, a woman of unscrupulous behaviour in the village. But there are other marriages in this novel which have turned into tragedy, sorrow and sin. The marriage of Rukmani’s eldest daughter, Ira and married life of Kunti tell tales of woe. It is also, by implication the story of the modernization of Indian villages. Rukmani is a traditional woman while Mira is a modern woman having Indian attitudes, culture and behavior.

The narrative thread is against put in the hands of a woman in “Some Inner Fury” 1955, the concept of family sentiment with the love experience of Mira and fight for the nation portrayed in it, unlike Nathan’s in *Nectar In A Sieve* is westernized and the central concern of the novel in the clash between passion and patriotism. In this novel contains a wider exploration, sociological and economic in the novels of Kamala Markandaya. She portrays a large repertoire of women in a changing Indian society.

In “A Silence Of Desire”, Sarojini Dandekar battles between tradition and modernity in contemporary India. Kamala Markandaya’s novels is an awareness of the socio - economic forces and their impact on women. So The protagonist, Sarojini in “A Silence Of Desire” is a good wife, mother and woman. She is a spiritual woman. She has all good qualities but she believes in a swamy and loses her time in the service of that swamy. She forgets her responsibilities towards her family and stands before the swamy. This spiritual and modernity conflict tries to break her family but fortunately her husband succeeds to put his wife from that trap.

Kamala Markandaya deals in all her novels with different attitudes of women. Saroja in “Two Virgins” and “Mira” in “Some Inner Fury” also deals with and narrates the story.. Her story is a love story with political crises. Saroja is a young woman, studying in a school, views about modernity. Her sister Lalitha is an advanced and modern girl and to go ahead she forgets all limitations and is engaged in evil. She becomes a film star and dazzles to see the lure of the film city. Lalitha is different from Rukmani and Mira. Despite all differences, Rukmani and Mira are superior than Lalitha. They never forget their limitations and remember their modesty and grace.

In the development of the Indian novel in English, the feminine sensibility has been assuredly well recognized, if a trifle overmuch and over - zealously at times by the Indian as well as foreign critics of Indian writing in English.

“Rukmani of *Nectar in a sieve* and Mira of *Some Inner Fury* recollect their tales in the comparative tranquility of a reverie- like style.” (Iyengar 332-333) Markandaya creates two totally different but compelling and compassionate narrators. Rukmani dominates her novel, Markandaya also successfully creates Mira as literate, city dweller woman dominating the novel. Both are perfected at their own level.

Mira is neither a flashy debutante nor a silly little rich girl but a thinking, independent, rather high – principled woman confused by the love. She feels for people who are at odds with each

other Mira pains takingly shows that her beloved Richard is an English man in a million, a veritable Fielding. Richard avoids the English community, is remarkably at home with Mira's family, relishes Indian food and clothing, knows stories from the Mahabharata, and is commonly gentle and gentle mainly is pressing his love for Mira. A pattern emerges in Markandaya's character sketches. Her women - Rukmani, Ira, Nalini, Mira, Roshan, Premala are all nobler, wiser, stronger, better than their male counterparts. But among the female characters, Rukmani is noble, ideal strong, wise, understood, patriot and liberal. Mira is literate, strong, powerful, modern, wise, patriot and understood. Rukmani is superior among all Indian views women and peasants women. Mira is superior among modern Indian women. Nalini in "A Handful Of Rice" is also good, lovely, beautiful, traditional and cooperative woman. She is superior to her elder sister Thangam and others who live in that society. Rukmani is narrator and victims of all events that happened with her and her surroundings. Nalini is not like Rukmani. She is neither a narrator nor an ideal for society. Roshan and Caroline in "Possession" are westernized and English women. Premala is also an Indian, city dweller and understood woman and die for the sake of the country. She has tried to be a modern as her husband wants. Modesty graces a woman. It is not right for a young woman to go among young men. Mira's mother comments about woman that a young woman should not go with young men it denours her personality and grace. Whenever we talk about marriage of a girl generally struck about dowry in mind. Most want dowry. It is rare ho are against this system. Kit is against this system he said,

"Was he to marry a woman for her money?"

But Mira's mother approach about this is that,

"the dowry is not for your benefit, it is

for the girl's self respect, that she may not have

to beg from you for her keep. You may be sure,

she said, the money will be in her name and the jewels will be upon her body".

(Markandaya Kamala 50-51)

A woman is supporter to a man in all aspect whether she is mother, wife, sister and friend. She suggests, guides and nurses him. Premala as a loving girl, is suitable for Kit. She cares for him as a wife and told Kit.

It shows the superiority of a woman. Modernity changes the mind of a people. Foreign returned Kit changd while he was an Indian but his thinking about dress, changed from Indianness to modernity. As he provoked Pramela in "Some Inner Fury", "You ought to try wearing shorts like Mira".(Markandaya Kamala 53) Pramele, an idol of an Indian woman tried to compromise with this modern man and lost the modesty of Indian woman, she "came to borrow my shorts. Put them on, blushing, blushed again, furiously, when Kit looked at her bare legs, for she had never worn anything but a sari. But this modesty, which is supposed to grace awoman, found little favour in Kits eyes".(Markandaya Kamala 53)

Markandaya takes as her characters - from a very wide spectrum : Indian peasants, students, Film producers, Indian émigrés in England, English engineers and their wives on contract service in India, English working class types culled from London pubs and suburban flats. Her women are peculiarly memorable - Rukmani, Mira, Caroline Bell, Saroja and Lalitha. And she has a particular interest in analyzing women characters and suggesting as in "Two Virgins" the unusual poignancy of their fate. The narrators too are likely to be female and even when not, the novel will be told mainly from a woman's viewpoint. It becomes clear what attracts Markandaya in human beings.

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